

METALLIC COMPLEXES OF TARTARIC AND CITRIC ACIDS. PART II. COPPER-ALKALI TARTRATE

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From conductometric measurements it has been shown that in dilute solution cupric ion reacts with alkali tartrate just like the free acid resulting in the formation of a complex containing metal and tartrate ion in the proportion of 1:1. By utilising Job's method of continued variation the instability constant of the complex has been determined. The mean value of K , the instability constant found, is 6.1×10^{-3} .

In a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 443) the results of the observations with tartaric acid were discussed. The present paper deals with the observations made with alkali tartrate by conductometric measurements. A summary with reference to the work done by various investigators on this issue had been included in Part I (*loc. cit.*). Although it was shown that copper reacted with alkali tartrate resulting in the formation of a complex containing metal and tartrate ion in the proportion of 1:1, no attempt was made to determine the stability of the complex formed. The author by utilising Job's method of continued variation (Job, *Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 928) has determined the instability constant of the complex.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions prepared from Merck's copper nitrate and Rochelle salt (as alkali tartrate) were used in all the measurements. Both copper and tartrate were estimated iodometrically.

Conductometric Measurements.—The same apparatus, as in the case with tartaric acid (*loc. cit.*), was used in all the conductometric measurements. Conductometric titration results are shown in Tables I and II and in curves I and II (Fig. 1). Conductance measurements in both equi- and non-equimolecular solutions were made in the same way as in case with tartaric acid (*loc. cit.*). Tables III-V contain the experimental data for equimolecular and VI-IX for non-equimolecular solutions respectively. Curves I-III (Fig. 2) and I-IV (Fig. 3) demonstrate, as in the case with tartaric acid, the divergence from the additivity rule plotted against composition of the mixture in the case of equi- and non-equimolecular solutions respectively. In the case of equimolecular solutions, one experiment (Table IV; curve II, Fig. 2) was performed by taking ammoniacal solution of copper nitrate (*i.e.* ammonia was added to copper nitrate solution till the precipitate formed dissolved and then diluted to the required volume) instead of a simple solution.

During measurements, in the case of higher concentrations of copper and tartrate solutions (up to $M/20$ strength), some mixtures in the neighbourhood of 1:1 became slightly turbid, if kept for some time. In those cases therefore readings were taken soon after mixing.

TABLE I

Conductometric titration of copper nitrate with Rochelle salt (R-salt).

M/50-Copper nitrate (50 c.c.) solution was taken in a cell and molar R-salt added. Initial value of the conductance (κ/R) of the copper nitrate solution = 58.8×10^{-4} . Temp. = 30° .

(cf. Fig. 1, curve I),

R-salt soln. added.	Increase of conductance over the initial value after each addition.	R-salt soln. added.	Increase of conductance over the initial value after each addition.	R-salt soln. added.	Increase of conductance over the initial value after each addition.
0 c.c.	0	1.0 c.c.	14.2×10^{-4}	2.0 c.c.	56.1×10^{-4}
0.2	3.7×10^{-4}	1.2	21.2	2.2	63.9
0.4	6.1	1.4	30.5	2.4	72.8
0.6	7.9	1.6	39.0	2.6	81.1
0.8	10.2	1.8	47.4	2.8	90.3

The increase in conductance, observed after each addition of R-salt solution over the initial value 58.8×10^{-4} , has been plotted against the ratio of copper to tartrate.

TABLE II

Conductometric titration of copper nitrate with Rochelle salt (R-salt).

M/75-Copper nitrate solution (50 c.c.) was taken in a cell and molar R-salt solution added. Initial value of the conductance (κ/R) of the copper nitrate solution = 43.1×10^{-4} . Temp. = 30° .

(cf. Fig. 1, curve II).

R-salt soln. added.	Increase of conductance over the initial value after each addition.	R-salt soln. added.	Increase of conductance over the initial value after each addition.	R-salt soln. added.	Increase of conductance over the initial value after each addition.
0 c.c.	0×10^{-4}	1.0 c.c.	21.0×10^{-4}	2.0 c.c.	65.6×10^{-4}
0.2	2.1	1.2	30.4	2.2	74.5
0.4	4.3	1.4	39.5	2.4	82.7
0.6	6.7	1.6	48.6	2.6	91.1
0.8	12.2	1.8	56.9	2.8	99.8

The increase in conductance observed after each addition of R-salt solution over the initial value 43.1×10^{-4} has been plotted against the ratio of copper to tartrate.

TABLE III

Conductivity experiment of *M/20-copper nitrate with M/20-Rochelle salt.*
Temp. = 30°. (cf Fig. 2, curve I).

Copper nitrate soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (1), each diluted to 50 c.c. = C_1 .	R-salt soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (3), each diluted to 50 c.c. = C_2 .	$(C_1 + C_2) = C_3$.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the mixture of solns. in cols. (1) and (3) = C_4 .	$(C_3 - C_4)$.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
50 c.c.	138.9	0 c.c.	...	138.9	138.9	0
45	126.0	5	17.5	142.5	126.6	15.9
40	112.4	10	31.3	143.7	116.3	27.4
35	100.0	15	45.5	145.5	105.8	39.7
32.5	94.1	17.5	52.1	146.2	101.5	44.7
30	88.5	20	58.1	146.6	95.2	51.4
27.5	80.7	22.5	64.1	144.8	89.3	55.5
25	74.1	25	70.9	145.0	87.0	58.0
22.5	68.0	27.5	76.9	144.9	88.3	56.6
20	59.9	30	83.3	143.2	91.7	51.5
17.5	54.1	32.5	89.3	143.4	95.0	48.4
16.7	51.3	33.3	90.9	142.2	97.1	45.1
15	46.5	35	96.2	142.7	99.0	43.7
10	31.6	40	107.5	139.1	107.5	31.6
5	17.5	45	117.6	135.1	115.6	19.5
...	...	50	130.7	130.7	130.7	0

TABLE IV

Conductivity expt. of *M/20-Rochelle salt and M/20-copper nitrate (ammoniacal).*
Temp. = 30°. (cf Fig. 2, curve II).

Copper nitrate soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (1), each diluted to 50 c.c. = C_1 .	R-salt soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (3), each diluted to 50 c.c. = C_2 .	$(C_1 + C_2) = C_3$.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the mixture of solns. in cols (1) and (3) = C_4 .	$(C_3 - C_4)$.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
50 c.c.	158.7	158.7	158.7	0
45	143.9	5 c.c.	17.5	161.4	149.3	12.1
40	129.9	10	32.3	162.2	139.9	22.3
35	115.6	15	47.2	162.8	133.3	29.3
32.5	108.7	17.5	53.8	162.5	130.7	31.8
30	100.0	20	60.6	160.6	128.2	32.4
27.5	93.5	22.5	67.1	160.6	126.1	34.5
25	87.0	25	74.1	161.1	125.0	36.1
22.5	79.4	27.5	80.0	159.4	125.8	33.6
20	70.9	30	87.0	157.9	126.6	31.3
17.5	61.4	32.5	93.2	154.6	127.8	26.8
15	54.1	35	99.0	153.1	129.0	24.1
10	38.0	40	111.1	149.1	131.1	18.0
...	...	50	135.1	135.1	135.1	0

TABLE V

Conductivity experiment of $M/30$ -Rochelle salt and $M/30$ -copper nitrate
Temp. = 30° . (cf. Fig. 2, curve III).

Copper nitrate soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (2), each being diluted to 50 c.c. = C_1 .	R-salt soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (3), each being diluted to 50 c.c. = C_2 .	$(C_1 + C_2) = C_3$.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the mixture of solns. in cols. (2) and (3) = C_4 .	$(C_3 - C_4)$.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
50 c.c.	95.2	0 c.c.	...	95.2	95.2	0
45	86.8	5	12.4	99.2	93.7	5.5
40	78.7	10	22.2	100.9	85.5	15.4
35	71.4	15	31.8	103.2	75.5	27.1
30	62.9	20	40.5	102.5	69.4	34.0
25	53.2	25	50.5	103.4	63.3	40.4
20	43.5	30	60.4	103.0	65.4	37.5
15	33.7	35	69.0	102.7	71.9	30.8
12.5	28.6	37.5	73.0	101.6	74.1	27.5
10	23.0	40	76.9	99.9	78.7	21.2
7.5	18.2	42.5	81.3	99.5	82.6	17.3
5	12.9	45	85.5	98.4	86.2	12.2
0	...	50	93.4	...	93.4	0

TABLE VI

Conductivity experiment of $M/20$ -copper nitrate and $M/10$ -Rochelle salt.
Temp. = 30° . (cf. Fig. 3, curve I).

Copper nitrate soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (2), each diluted to 50 c.c. = C_1 .	R-salt soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (3), each diluted to 50 c.c. = C_2 .	$(C_1 + C_2) = C_3$.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the mixture of solns. in cols. (2) and (3) = C_4 .	$(C_3 - C_4)$.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
50 c.c.	146.0	146.0	146.0	0
40	119.0	10 c.c.	62.5	179.5	121.2	58.3
35	105.3	15	89.3	194.6	123.5	71.1
33.3	97.8	16.7	99.7	197.5	124.2	73.3
32.5	95.2	17.5	104.7	199.9	125.0	74.9
31	94.3	19	111.1	205.4	129.4	76.0
30.5	93.2	19.5	113.6	206.8	130.2	76.6
30	91.7	20	116.3	208.0	131.6	76.4
27.5	85.2	22.5	130.7	215.9	144.9	71.0
25	76.9	25	140.8	217.7	152.7	65.0
22.5	71.4	27.5	155.0	226.4	162.6	63.8
20	64.5	30	166.7	231.2	173.9	57.3
15	49.0	35	190.5	239.5	190.5	49.0
10	33.9	40	212.8	251.8	215.1	36.7
...	...	50	259.7	259.7	259.7	0

TABLE VII

Conductivity experiment of $M/30$ -copper nitrate and $M/10$ -Rochelle salt.
Temp. = 30° . (cf. Fig. 3, curve II).

Copper nitrate soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (1), each diluted to 50 c.c. = C_1 .	R-salt soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (3), each diluted to 50 c.c. = C_3 .	$(C_1 + C_3) = C_2$.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the mixture of solns. in cols. (1) and (3) = C_4 .	$(C_2 - C_4)$.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
50 c.c.	98.0	—	—	98.5	98.5	0
40	80.7	10 c.c.	61.4	142.1	92.6	49.5
37.5	75.8	12.5	74.6	150.4	94.3	56.1
35	71.4	15	88.5	159.9	101.0	58.9
33.5	69.9	16.5	97.1	167.0	107.5	59.5
33	68.7	17	100.0	168.7	108.7	60.0
32.5	67.8	17.5	102.0	169.8	110.5	59.3
30	62.5	20	114.3	176.8	120.5	56.3
27.5	58.8	22.5	126.6	185.4	131.6	53.8
25	54.1	25	138.9	193.0	144.9	48.1
20	43.9	30	162.6	206.5	166.7	39.8
15	33.9	35	183.5	217.4	185.9	31.5
10	23.8	40	206.2	230.0	208.3	21.7
—	—	50	250.0	250.0	250.0	0

TABLE VIII

Conductivity experiment of $M/50$ -copper nitrate and $M/10$ -Rochelle salt.
Temp. = 30° . (cf. Fig. 3, curve III).

Copper nitrate soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (1), each diluted to 50 c.c. = C_1 .	R-salt soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (3), each diluted to 50 c.c. = C_3 .	$(C_1 + C_3) = C_2$.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the mixture of solns. in cols. (1) and (3) = C_4 .	$(C_2 - C_4)$.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
50 c.c.	60.6	0 c.c.	—	60.6	60.6	0
45	55.6	5	31.3	86.9	62.5	24.4
40	51.3	10	59.5	110.8	71.4	39.4
37.5	48.3	12.5	74.6	122.9	80.0	42.9
36.5	47.4	13.5	80.0	127.4	83.3	44.1
36	47.0	14	82.6	129.6	85.2	44.4
35.5	46.3	14.5	84.8	131.1	87.0	44.1
35	45.7	15	87.0	132.7	89.3	43.4
32.5	42.6	17.5	101.0	143.6	102.0	41.6
30	39.2	20	111.1	150.3	111.1	39.2
25	33.0	25	134.2	167.2	131.6	35.6
20	27.0	30	160.0	187.0	156.2	30.8
10	14.7	40	200.0	214.7	198.0	16.7
0	—	50	232.6	232.6	232.6	0

TABLE IX

Conductivity experiment of $M/40$ -copper nitrate and $M/16$ -Rochelle salt.Temp. = 30° . (cf. Fig. 3, curve IV).

Copper nitrate soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (3), each diluted to 50 c.c. = C_1 .	R-salt soln.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the soln. in col. (3), each diluted to 50 c.c. = C_2 .	$(C_1 + C_2) = C_3$.	$(1/R) \times 10^4$ of the mixture of solns. in cols. (1) and (3) = C_4 .	$(C_3 - C_4)$.
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
50 c.c.	75.2	0 c.c.	—	75.2	75.2	0
40	60.6	10	38.5	99.1	67.6	31.5
35	53.5	15	55.6	109.1	68.0	41.1
32.5	50.5	17.5	64.5	115.0	72.5	42.5
31.5	48.5	18.5	69.0	117.5	74.1	43.4
30	46.5	20	74.1	120.6	76.9	42.1
27.5	43.5	22.5	81.3	124.8	84.8	40.0
25	40.0	25	87.7	127.7	91.7	36.0
22.5	36.8	27.5	94.3	131.1	99.0	32.1
20	32.7	30	103.1	135.8	105.3	30.5
15	25.3	35	119.0	144.3	119.0	25.3
10	15.2	40	132.5	147.7	132.5	15.2
—	—	50	172.4	172.4	172.4	0

DISCUSSION

It is observed from the conductometric titration curves (curves I-II, Fig. 1) that a sharp break occurs in the proportion of 1:1. Therefore it can be concluded that the reaction occurs in that proportion. The same conclusion is also supported by the results of conductance measurements of equimolecular solutions at various concentrations in which a maximum is obtained in each case in that proportion when the divergence from the additivity rule due to complex formation is plotted against composition of the mixture (curves I-III, Fig. 2).

FIG. 1

1:0 1:1 1:2 1:3 1:4
 Ratio of copper to tartrate.
 I-50 c.c. $M/50$ - $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M$ -R-salt.
 II-50 c.c. $M/75$. $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M$ -R-salt.

FIG. 2

50 40 30 20 10 0
 $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in c.c.
 I- $M/20$ - $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/20$ -R-salt.
 II- Do. (ammon) + Do.
 III- $M/30$ - $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/30$ - "

From the experimental results therefore it can be definitely concluded that in dilute solution one and only one complex is formed between cupric and tartrate ion ($\text{Cu}^{++} + \text{T}'' \rightleftharpoons \text{CuT}$, where $\text{T}'' = \text{tartrate ion}$) and that in the proportion of 1 : 1.

Now by applying Job's method of continued variation (*loc. cit.*) the instability constant can be found out from the measurement of conductance in non-equimolecular solutions.

Calculations of K, the Instability Constant

The equation relating to value of K is given by

$$K = \frac{C \{(p+1)x - 1\}^2}{(p-1)(1-2x)}$$

where C is the molar concentration of copper nitrate, p , the molar concentration of Rochelle salt (R-salt) and x c.c. of R-salt reacting with $(1-x)$ c.c. of copper nitrate to give the maximum effect.

TABLE X

Table No.	Fig. No.	Curve No.	C .	p .	x .	$K \times 10^3$.	Mean $K \times 10^3$
VI	3	I	0.050	2	0.39	6.6	
VII	3	II	0.033	3	0.34	6.7	
VIII	3	III	0.020	5	0.28	5.3	6.1
IX	3	IV	0.025	2.5	0.37	5.8	

FIG. 3

Curves I-IV refers respectively to $M/20\text{-Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/10\text{-R-salt}$, $M/30\text{-Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/10\text{-R-salt}$ and $M/50\text{-Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/16\text{-R-salt}$.

Although the complex formed in the case of tartaric acid and alkali tartrate is the same (CuT), there is some divergence in the value of K as obtained in the two cases. The value in the former case (with tartaric acid) is 9.6×10^{-3} and in the latter (with alkali tartrate) 6.1×10^{-3} . This variation is due to the fact, as has already been discussed (Part I, *loc. cit.*), that the neutral complex formed is less stable in presence of free hydrogen ion liberated by the reaction in case with tartaric acid and as a result the stability is affected by the presence of free hydrogen ion. It is observed that nature of the conductometric titration curves with tartaric acid and alkali tartrate differs considerably. In case of the former a rather continuous curve is obtained, whereas in the latter case a well defined break signifies the complex formation.

The observations from absorption measurements with alkali tartrate will be the subject matter of the next paper.

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